

Highlights

- High- and low-coercivity (3.70 kOe or 0.25 kOe) cobalt ferrite nanoparticles (33 nm and 12 nm, respectively) were produced.
- Microstructure and magnetic properties were tailored by designing the milling treatment.
- Crystallite size and strain contribute to the shift from the Néel model (increasing of the spin-canting angle).
- For the magnetic domain wall motion small magnetic defects show a pinning effect larger than extended planar inhomogeneities.

Easy batch-scale production of cobalt ferrite nanopowders by two-step milling: structural and magnetic characterization

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Abstract

Cobalt ferrite (CF) powder was synthesized by solid state reaction method at two different calcination temperatures (1120 K and 1320 K) then milled in two steps, gradually reducing the milling media size. The first milling step results in CF nanoparticles with crystallite size of 33 nm showing fairly high coercivity (3.7 kOe), more than 5 times higher than the non-milled material (0.7 kOe). The high coercivity has been correlated was correlated to the crystallite size close to the single-domain limit, and to the strain increase up to 2.1%. This value of strain is the highest ever reported in literature for the CF and brings to the highest figure of merit for permanent magnets, $(BH)_{max} = 2.16$ MGOe. After the second milling step the powder displays particle size of 9 nm, release of strain ($\epsilon = 1.2\%$), coercivity reduction that approaches 250 Oe and decrease of the deblocking temperature from 421 K to 317 K. The large tunability obtained by multi-step milling allows to use CF in different applications. In particular, the milled CF powder characterized by high microstrain is a good candidate for the realization of rare-earth-free permanent magnets (at least on the basis of the $(BH)_{max}$ product). For the first time, a correlation between the spin-canting angle and the degree of inversion, the crystallite size and the microstrain is presented and discussed.

Keywords

Néel model; spin-canting angle; magnetic anisotropy; magnetic inhomogeneities; initial susceptibility; maximum energy product;

Introduction

The production of cobalt ferrite (CF) nanopowders is receiving even more attention and increasing demand as they can be used in novel large-scale applications in the catalysis and environmental fields [1-3], and in the sustainable energy conversion [4, 5]. The large tunability of CF makes it possible to replace rare-earth (RE)-based permanent magnets in a wide range of applications, such as hard disks, wind turbines, and hybrid-electric vehicles [6], or to implement the performance of devices used in sensing and biomedical applications as a contrast agent for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and heat mediator for Magnetic Fluid Hyperthermia (MFH) [7]. Spinel ferrite nanopowders are mainly synthesized by coprecipitation, hydrothermal and sol-gel methods [8-10] and aiming at modifying the magnetic properties by changing the processing parameters and/or the stoichiometry [11-13]. The efficient use of CF, and, in general, ferrimagnetic compound materials, is dependent on improving their design and controlling their microstructure [14]. The particle size affects the crystal structure, and the above methods are successfully adopted to reach the optimal particle size and shape [6, 15, 16]. On the other hand, the effect of extrinsic parameters (i.e. pH, temperature, and molecular concentration) on the crystallite size, morphology, defects, strains, chemical composition (i.e. Co depletion), and cation distribution during synthesis are difficult to control also at the laboratory scale, and even small changes of the process parameters can lead to significant changes in the final properties [17]. Magnetic nanoparticles with coercivity (H_c) of 2-3 kOe can be obtained by sol-gel methods, processes more difficult to control and more time-consuming [18]. Remarkable efforts are made to increase the coercivity at room temperature. Coercivity values of 5-6 kOe - while keeping a relatively small decrease in magnetic saturation (M_s) - were obtained with doped CF nanoparticles prepared by chemical route [12]. To our knowledge, the highest H_c value obtained for CF nanopowders is 9.5 kOe after capping it with oleic acid; but this remarkable H_c increase was reached at the expense of M_s which was decreased about ten times [19]. It was suggested that the high coercivity (9.5 kOe) is the result of strain and disorder of the surface spin due to the chemical absorption of oleic acid. Another strategy to improve the

coercivity aimed at increasing the defects density and the residual strain of the nanoparticles by mechanical milling synthesis [20]. This approach led to a maximum coercivity of 5.1 kOe [21]. In particular, for cubic spinel ferrites, it was demonstrated that 2D defects such as dislocations [21] and twin boundaries on {111} planes [22] (coherent twin boundaries along the four crystallographic hard axes across the body diagonals denoted as $\langle 111 \rangle$), appear like magnetic inhomogeneities [23] and act as the effective pinning centers for the hindrance of domain wall movement across the six crystallographic easy axes (direction) along the cube edges of the crystal denoted as $\langle 100 \rangle$.

In this work CF powders were synthesized by solid state reaction in order to achieve a batch-scale production, easy scalability, with high repeatability and reliability, and low cost. The two-step planetary milling treatment was designed starting from a previous study on milling, where we found the correlation between milling efficiency and starting planetary milling setup and CF particle size distribution [22]. The aim of the first milling step was to produce stressed and highly defective particles in order to investigate the effect of very high level of residual strain ($> 1\%$) on the microstructural and magnetic properties. It is worth underlining that, as high-density defects and high-level strain in nanopowders can be easily released during aging (this phenomena should be investigated in future works), the second milling step was aimed at releasing the plastic strain [24] and achieving smaller nanosized powders with narrow particle size distribution. This approach is promising in view to engineer the CF powders for applications from those where high coercivity is required such as permanent magnets applications, to the others where superparamagnetic behaviour is needed such as MRI or MFH. A detailed study on the microstructural evolution during mechanical milling and its effect on the magnetic properties on CF powders is presented.

1. Method

1.1. Sample-preparation

Cobalt ferrite (CoFe_2O_4 , CF in the following) powders were synthesized by solid state reaction (SSR) of microsized cobalt oxide powder (Co_3O_4 , Alfa Aesar 45806), and microsized iron oxide ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, Aldrich 310050). The powders were mixed with pure ethanol in a polyethylene bottle at room temperature, and milled for 48 h with zirconia balls. The powders were then dried and heat-treated at different temperatures and soaking times. In this study, the following calcination conditions were employed: 1120 K for 12 h

(CF₁₁), and 1320 K for 4 h (CF₁₃). The heat-treated powders were further wet-milled in two-step at room temperature by planetary milling (PM) at 400 rpm in a stainless steel jar of 250 cm³ filled to 75 vol.% with pure ethanol. In the first step (M_I), 50 g of powders were milled for 12 h in 36 steps (with pauses of 5 min between steps) using zirconia balls of 5 mm diameter, and a balls/powders mass ratio of 11.2 (samples: CF₁₁M_I, and CF₁₃M_I). In the second step (M_{II}), only 40 g of the previously milled powders were further milled for 28 h in 84 steps (with pauses of 5 min between steps) using zirconia balls of 1 mm diameter, and a balls/powders mass ratio of 14 (samples: CF₁₁M_{II}, and CF₁₃M_{II}).

1.2. Characterization

The morphology of the obtained powders was examined with a FEI Quanta Inspect F scanning electron microscope (SEM). Image-Pro Analyzer 7.0 software was used to measure the particle size. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns of the powders were obtained at room temperature on a Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer (θ - θ) equipped with a LINXEYE detector (Bruker, Karlsruhe, Germany) using Cu K $_{\alpha}$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) in the $15^{\circ} \leq 2\theta \leq 80^{\circ}$ range, at 2.4 $^{\circ}$ /min scanning rate. The crystalline phases were identified by using the commercial BRUKER EVA program. The Rietveld refinement method was carried out by using the GSAS-II software [25] in order to refine both the structural (lattice constants, atomic positions, site occupancies, and bond lengths and angles) and microstructural parameters (crystallite size and lattice strain). The peak profiles were fitted using pseudo-Voigt function while a sixth-order polynomial equation was used to fit the background. The Marquardt least-squares procedure was carried out in order to minimize the difference between the observed and simulated powder diffraction patterns until the goodness of fit (χ^2) factor became lower than 1.3 [26, 27]. Mössbauer measurements were performed at room temperature with WissEL-ICE Oxford Mössbauer cryomagnetic system. The γ -rays were provided by a ⁵⁷Co source in a rhodium matrix. To avoid the additional contributions to the line widths the thickness of the samples was calculated at $\sim 7 \text{ mg/cm}^2$. The magnetic properties of CF powders were investigated using a Quantum Design MPMS-5S SQUID magnetometer, in the temperature range of 5 K - 355 K and an applied magnetic field of up to 65 kOe. Zero-field-cooled (ZFC) magnetizations were measured by cooling the samples in a zero magnetic field and then increasing the temperature up to 390 K in a static field of 100 Oe, while field-cooled (FC) curves were obtained by cooling the samples in the same static field.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Particle morphology

Fig.1 shows the as calcined CF_{11} and CF_{13} powders (Fig.1 (a) and (b)), and their morphology after the first milling step (CF_{11}M_I and CF_{13}M_I powders, Fig.1 (c) and (d)) and after the second milling step ($\text{CF}_{11}\text{M}_{II}$ and $\text{CF}_{13}\text{M}_{II}$ powders, Fig.1 (e) and (f)). The powders calcined at higher temperature (1323 K) show larger particle size, characterized by well-defined euhedral grains (faceted and twinned [22]) than those calcined at 1123 K (Fig.1 (a) and (b)). After the first milling step (12 h with 5 mm diameter milling media), both CF powders were milled down to nanoscale (Fig.1 (c) and (d)). The particle size (PS) density distribution is peaked at about 30 nm, and covers particles from 13 nm to 300 nm (Fig.1 (g) and (h)). The decrease of milling media size down to 1 mm and the increase of the milling time up to 28 h resulted into significantly reduced particle size of both nanopowders with mean particles size of 11 nm for the $\text{CF}_{11}\text{M}_{II}$ sample. Even smaller size was achieved for $\text{CF}_{13}\text{M}_{II}$ (70 % of the particles is smaller than 11 nm) where particles bigger than 20 nm remained and the particle size density distribution is not as narrow as for the $\text{CF}_{11}\text{M}_{II}$ sample. It is worth noticing that with the two milling steps small particle sizes of the SSR powders were achieved (10 – 100 nm) comparable with those obtained with wet chemical synthesis processes such as the precipitation methods [8, 15, 18, 19, 21].

Fig. 1 SEM morphology of as calcined (a) CF₁₁ and (b) CF₁₃ powders; after the first milling step (c) CF₁₁M_I and (d) CF₁₃M_I powders ; and after the second milling step (e) CF₁₁M_{II} and (f) CF₁₃M_{II} powders. The cumulative curves show the measured PS values through image analysis of the SEM micrographs. The corresponding particle size density distributions were obtained by deriving the fitting of the experimental points. The cumulative curves of the as-calcined and the two times milled powders were fitted through the SGompertz model implemented in OringPro 9.1 software, while for the powders milled one time the biphasic Dose response function was used. (two- column)

2.2. XRD patterns analysis

The general structural formula of cobalt ferrite can be represented as follows:

where the variable i is the degree of inversion and describes the fraction of the tetrahedral sites (A) (coordination number of four) and octahedral sites [B] (coordination number of six) occupied by Fe³⁺ and Co²⁺ cations, respectively. If $i = 1$ the structure is called inverse spinel; if $i = 0$ the structure is called normal spinel, otherwise it is called mixed spinel or partially inverse. The spinel structure belongs to the space group Fd₃m – O_h⁷ (no. 227), and to the crystallographic family cF56. The unit cell contains 32 O²⁻ anions distributed in a close packed fcc structure, 24 cations occupying 8 of the 64 available (A)-sites, and 16 of the 32 available [B]-sites, for a total number of 56 ions on 128 lattice sites.

After calcination at 1323 K for 4 h, the XRD (Fig.2) confirms the formation of pure CoFe₂O₄ with inverse spinel structure without any other phase, while the reaction yield of the calcination at 1123 K for 12 h amounted to 94 wt% as it can be seen from the hematite peak highlighted in Fig.2. In both cases, CF₁₁ and CF₁₃, the produced CF reached its equilibrium, since at equilibrium CF is an inverse spinel at ambient temperature [28]. This result is due to the much higher calcination temperature respect to the temperature of full transformation into CF of the stoichiometric precursor oxides (1013.5 K [29]). The residual amount after calcination at 1123 K for 12 h (4 wt% of Fe₂O₃ and 2 wt% of Co₃O₄ not shown in the figure due to very low amount) depends on temperature/time controlled diffusion and reaction distance, i.e. starting particles sizes in the micron scale. In fact, in a previous work, the full transformation into CF was achieved after calcination of the nanopowders at 1123 K for 2 h [22]. The performed milling treatments strongly influence the CF

microstructure as it can be seen from the increase of peaks broadening and the abrupt reduction of their intensity (Fig.2). The microstructural evolution towards the non-equilibrium configuration was investigated through Rietveld analysis and results are reported in Tab. 1.

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the as calcined CF powders and after planetary milling treatments. All the patterns were collected in the same conditions. CF peaks are labelled with the respective Miller indices. The arrow points the highest peak of the unreacted hematite (α - Fe_2O_3). (*single column*)

	CF	ρ_x	a	D	ε	$I_{(220)}/I_{(222)}$	χ^2	
	(wt %)	(g/cm^3)	(\AA)	(nm)	(%)			
	CF ₁₁	93	5.309	8.373	307	0.08	4.6	1.142
	CF ₁₁ M _I	97	5.281	8.388	31	1.96	3.0	1.081
	CF ₁₁ M _{II}	99	5.234	8.413	12	0.61	2.1	1.092
	CF ₁₃	100	5.307	8.374	369	0.00	4.7	1.179
	CF ₁₃ M _I	100	5.287	8.385	33	2.11	2.9	1.105
	CF ₁₃ M _{II}	100	5.291	8.383	9	1.18	1.9	1.004

Tab. 1 – Cobalt ferrite weight percentage (first column), crystallographic density (ρ_x), lattice parameter (a), average crystallite size (D), strain percentage (ε), and intensity $I_{(220)}/I_{(222)}$ ratio calculated by Rietveld

refinement [25]. χ^2 is the goodness of fit and depicts the refinement fitting parameters, $\chi^2 < 2$ is generally accepted [27]

The as-calcined powders display crystallographic density (ρ_x) and lattice parameter (a) values in good agreement with their bulk value of 5.304 g/cm³ and 8.377Å, respectively. This result demonstrates the achieved equilibrium of the CF synthesized by SSR. The ρ_x reduction and a increasing with the milling treatments can be explained with the reduction of the spinel inversion degree (i) under the induced mechanical stress. Similar conclusions were presented by Zi *et al.* which correlated the reduced lattice parameter to the i increase [30]. As said above, in the spinel lattice, only one eighth of the tetrahedral sites and half of the octahedral sites are occupied by cations. This large fraction of empty interstitial sites makes the spinel structure a very open structure for the cation diffusion. Thus, during the milling, the relatively larger Co²⁺ ions (0.72 Å) can be forced to occupy the tetrahedral sites leaving their conventionally preferred octahedral sites to the Fe³⁺ ions (0.64 Å). Taking into account that tetrahedral sites are smaller than the octahedral ones, a higher occupancy of the tetrahedral sites by Co²⁺ ions leads to an expansion of the structure and, consequently, to an increase of the lattice parameter of the milled nanoparticles. This scenario can be confirmed by the variation of the intensity $I_{(220)}/I_{(222)}$ ratio which provides information about the variation of cations distribution. In particular, the i decrease corresponds to a decrease of intensity ratio. Moreover, it is well known that CF nanoparticles tend to keep partially inverse structures with about $i = 0.7 - 0.8$ [27, 31] and $I_{(220)}/I_{(222)} = 3.25$ [32]. Milling-induced cation redistribution was also reported by Ref.'s [21, 33].

The crystallite size (D) and intrinsic strain (ε) of the CF nanoparticles (Tab. 1) are determined from the Lorentzian coefficients according to GSAS manual [25]. In Fig.3 the Lorentzian broadening contribution on the integral breadth of the XRD peaks (β) is shown as a function of D and ε , according to the Williamson-Hall (W-H) methods [34]:

$$\beta \cos(\theta) = 0.9 \lambda / D + 4\varepsilon \sin(\theta) \quad (2)$$

The calculated crystallite sizes are in agreement with SEM analysis (Fig.1) and XRD peak broadening (Fig.2). In particular, the calculated values show that the multidomains as-calcined particles achieve an

average crystallite size close to the single-domain limit (28 nm [15]) after the first milling step, and close to the superparamagnetic limit (6 nm [35]) after the second milling step. A further important result is the very high level of microstrain induced by milling on the CF powder synthesized by SSR ($\varepsilon \approx 2\%$) respect to the CF synthesized by precipitation method and then milled ($\varepsilon < 1\%$) [20, 21, 33]. It is well known that initial particle size plays an important role in the milling efficiency and thus in the microstructural evolution [21, 22], and that the nanoparticles become less able to arrange microstrain when their crystallite size decreases [21, 36]. These considerations can explain the different milling effect on the CF powders calcined at 1123 K and 1323 K in terms of crystallite size and microstrain evolution during milling step. From the W-H plot (Fig.3) it is easy to compare the microstructural evolution of the two powders since the y-intercept and the slope of the curves are linearly proportional to ε and $1/D$, respectively. The small slope of CF₁₁ sample, which corresponds to $\varepsilon = 0.08\%$, can be due to lattice mismatch between the CF grains and the unreacted fraction of oxides. The CF₁₁M_I and CF₁₃M_I curves are quite similar, while the CF₁₃M_{II} curve has a higher y-intercept than the CF₁₁M_{II} curve as it is demonstrated by the almost completely smoothed XRD spectra (Fig.2) and lower average crystallite size (Tab. 1).

Fig. 3 Williamson-Hall plot obtained from the Lorentzian broadening contribution measured with Rietveld refinement. (*single column*)

2.4. Mössbauer Analysis

The Mössbauer spectra at room temperature (not shown here) of as-sintered and milled powders consist in magnetic hyperfine patterns, without any superparamagnetic contribution. The cation distribution was calculated from the following equation [37]:

$$i = 2 A_{Td} / (1.2 A_{Oh} + A_{Td}) \quad (3)$$

where the A_{Td} and A_{Oh} are the areas corresponding to the tetrahedral and octahedral sites, respectively, occupied by Fe^{3+} cations. In Tab. 2 the calculated i values together with the related Mössbauer parameters are reported for the $CF_{13}M_I$ and $CF_{13}M_{II}$ samples. The inversion degree of the samples calcined at 1123 K was not calculated because they are not pure CF. These results confirm the above discussion about the cation distribution in function of the crystallite size. **The absence of Fe^{2+} cations signal excludes that Co^{3+} cations enter in the iron spinel lattice since the charge neutrality must be preserved. The replacement of Fe^{2+} with the more anisotropic Co^{2+} cation enhances the magneto-crystalline anisotropy that is a key parameter for the applications of this material [7].**

Sample	A_{Td}	A_{Oh}	i	$(Co_{1-i}Fe_i)[Co_iFe_{2-i}]O_4$
$CF_{13}M_I$	0.29	0.71	0.51	$(Co_{0.49}Fe_{0.51})[Co_{0.51}Fe_{1.49}]O_4$
$CF_{13}M_{II}$	0.22	0.78	0.38	$(Co_{0.62}Fe_{0.38})[Co_{0.38}Fe_{1.62}]O_4$

Tab. 2 - Normalized tetrahedral and octahedral areas together with the inversion parameter and cation distribution of the samples

2.5. Magnetic properties

The magnetic hysteresis loops (Fig.4) indicate that all the samples have ferromagnetic properties. The coercive field (H_c) and the remnant magnetization (M_r) values (reported in Tab. 3 and Tab. 4) are the interception of the hysteresis loops with abscissa and ordinate axes, respectively. The obtained coercivity values are in agreement with the values reported in the literature and fit the expected values in reference to the crystallite size: i) 0.4 kOe – 1 kOe for multidomain particles [6, 32, 38]; ii) 3 kOe – 5 kOe for particle equal or close to the single domain limit [6, 20, 36]; iii) 0 kOe – 3 kOe for particle smaller than single domain limit [6, 18, 36, 38] (the reported reference values refer to properties at room temperature). **The nonmonotonous dependence of H_c on the crystallite size can be affected by the combination of particle shape [6] and strain level [33]. In particular, the high level of strain induced by milling increases the coercivity value acting as pinning centre [21, 33].** Using the law of approach to saturation – which describes the dependence of magnetization of ferromagnetic materials on the applied field for $H > H_c$ [39] – Saturation magnetization (M_s) and cubic anisotropy constant (K_I) were estimated through a nonlinear fitting solved by

Levenberg Marquardt interaction algorithm (the damped least-squares method used to solve non-linear least squares problems). In particular for randomly oriented polycrystalline specimens with cubic anisotropy, the magnetization near M_s is described by the following equation [39]:

$$M = M_s \{1 - 8/105 [K_1/(M_s H)]^2 - 4/105 [K_1/(M_s H)]^3\} + \kappa H \quad (4)$$

In the above Eq. 4 κH is the forced magnetization, also called the paramagnetism-like term, caused by an increase in the spontaneous magnetization itself (proportional to high-field susceptibility, κ) at high field and high temperatures [40]. The law of approach, written above, is valid in the range $0.97 M_s < M < M_s$ (when the rotation of the magnetic moments is activated), and neglects the contribution of inclusion and microstress (proportional to $1/H$).

Fig. 4 Magnetisation (M) versus magnetic field strength (H) curves at 300 K (first row), 100 K (second row), and 5 K (third row) of CF_{11} (first column) and CF_{13} (second column) samples after calcination (square symbol), after first milling (circular symbol), and after second milling (triangular symbol). (*two-column*)

Tab. 3 and Tab. 4 summarize the parameters obtained from these fittings for the CF₁₁ and CF₁₃ samples, respectively. It is worth notice that M_S values of as calcined CF₁₁ and CF₁₃ powders match the M_S values of bulk CF (80 – 94 emu/g) and also those reported for highly crystalline CF nanoparticles. The milling treatments decrease the M_S (the samples calcined at 1123 K display a different trend as the CF amount increases during the milling, Tab. 1) first and foremost, since the size reduction in the nanoscale increases the spin disordered surface layer which requires a larger field to be saturated. Moreover the structural distortion in the surface can configure a “magnetically dead” surface layer compared to the bulk in which it could reduce the number of moments contributing [40]. On the other hand, the crystallite size reduction by milling treatment allowed the i reduction which should increase the saturation magnetization. In fact, according with Néel model, if we consider a complete inverse spinel cobalt ferrite, $i = 1$, half of the Fe³⁺ cations (magnetic moment equal to $5 \mu_B$) occupy the (A)-sites and the other half the [B]-sites, together with Co²⁺ cations. And, since the magnetic moments of the ions in the (A) and [B] sites are aligned in an anti-parallel way, the magnetic contributions of the Fe³⁺ cations are mutually compensated. Therefore, the net magnetic moment of the complete inverse spinel cobalt ferrite is the sum of the Co²⁺ moments on the [B]-sites (magnetic moment equal to $3 \mu_B$). When i decreases toward 0 (normal spinel), it means that Co²⁺ cations moved from [B]-sites to (A)-sites and consequently Fe³⁺ cations diffused from (A)-sites to [B]-sites; this cation distribution increases the net magnetic moment of the material, and, consequently, promotes an increase in M_S . The expression for the total magnetization of spinel oxide (M_T), expressed in the units of Bohr magneton (μ_B), is given as [41]:

$$M_T = M_S M_W / 5585 = M_{[B]} \cos(\phi) - M_{(A)} \quad (5)$$

where M_W is the molecular weight, $M_{[B]}$ and $M_{(A)}$ are the magnetic contributions of cations at the octahedral and tetrahedral sites in μ_B units, respectively, and ϕ is the spin canting angle between the [B] site moments.

	T	H_c	$\chi_{\text{irr-p}}$	M_r	M_s	M_r/M_s	K_I	K_{eff}	$(BH)_{\text{max}}$	
	(K)	(Oe)	(Oe)	(emu/g)	(emu/g)		(Merg/cm ³)	(Merg/cm ³)	(MGOe)	
CF ₁₁	300	1027	±14	2012	22 ±0	78 ±0	0.28 ±0.00	3.4 ±0.2	3.9	0.38
CF ₁₁ M ₁	300	3080	±34	5034	25 ±0	54 ±2	0.47 ±0.02	4.7 ±1.4	46.2	1.34

CF ₁₁ M _{II}	300	254	±6	505	8	±0	58	±0	0.14	±0.00	3.5	±0.4	14.7	0.03
CF ₁₁	100	4380	±46	4034	64	±0	79	±0	0.81	±0.00	5.4	±0.2	5.7	6.15
CF ₁₁ M _I	100	8742	±88	12057	39	±0	62	±2	0.62	±0.02	7.5	±0.5	46.5	7.22
CF ₁₁ M _{II}	100	3745	±40	4029	38	±0	68	±0	0.56	±0.00	4.7	±0.0	15.0	2.89
CF ₁₁	5	5947	±61	5037	69	±0	81	±1	0.84	±0.01	10.8	±0.2	11.0	9.93
CF ₁₁ M _I	5	13503	±134	15832	45	±0	67	±3	0.67	±0.03	11.7	±1.0	47.4	14.55
CF ₁₁ M _{II}	5	8652	±87	9.048	52	±0	74	±1	0.71	±0.01	9.1	±0.3	16.9	11.23

Tab. 3 - Magnetic Properties at 300 K, 100 K and 5 K of CF₁₁ series

	<i>T</i>	<i>H_c</i>	χ_{irr-p}	<i>M_r</i>	<i>M_s</i>	<i>M_r/M_s</i>	<i>K_I</i>	<i>K_{eff}</i>	<i>(BH)_{max}</i>					
	(K)	(Oe)	(Oe)	(emu/g)	(emu/g)		(Merg/cm ³)	(Merg/cm ³)	(MGOe)					
CF ₁₃	300	701	±11	1510	19	±0	82	±0	0.23	±0.00	3.4	±0.3	3.4	0.23
CF ₁₃ M _I	300	3719	±40	5023	31	±0	58	±0	0.53	±0.00	4.6	±0.8	49.7	2.16
CF ₁₃ M _{II}	300	931	±13	522	13	±0	54	±1	0.24	±0.01	5.0	±1.2	28.1	0.18
CF ₁₃	100	3291	±36	3026	66	±0	83	±0	0.80	±0.00	5.0	±0.5	5.0	4.09
CF ₁₃ M _I	100	9609	±96	12060	44	±0	68	±1	0.65	±0.01	8.5	±0.8	50.2	9.40
CF ₁₃ M _{II}	100	5734	±59	7544	33	±0	62	±1	0.53	±0.01	6.7	±0.7	28.4	3.48
CF ₁₃	5	4737	±50	4029	71	±0	85	±1	0.83	±0.01	9.1	±1.6	9.1	6.83
CF ₁₃ M _I	5	14056	±139	16243	50	±0	76	±2	0.66	±0.02	14.7	±0.6	51.6	17.54
CF ₁₃ M _{II}	5	12508	±124	15833	45	±0	69	±1	0.65	±0.01	12.0	±0.4	27.7	12.53

Tab. 4 - Magnetic Properties at 300 K, 100 K and 5 K of CF₁₃ series

In Fig.5 the variation of ϕ is plotted as function of *i*. The linear increase in spin canting angles with the decrease in inversion degree suggests the decreasing in exchange interaction between (A) and [B] cations in cubic spinel ferrite, and the consequent decrease of the total magnetization according with the Eq. 5 and the experimental evidences (the milling treatments decrease the *M_s*). In particular it was found that $\phi = 0^\circ$ for *i* = 1, and ϕ should approach 72° for *i* = 0 (calculated through the linear fit plotted in Fig.5). This means that with

the decreasing of i , randomness and frustration increase and show significant departure from the Néel-type collinear magnetic order ($\phi = 0^\circ$). This is reasonable since we found that i is proportional to D , thus i decreases as the size of the nanoparticles reduces the surface to volume ratio and the dead layer becomes more prominent [40]. On the other hand, it was found that ϕ increases at the decreasing of i as a consequence of the intrinsic strain ε increase [36], and that the nanoparticles are less and less able to arrange microstrain due to Co^{2+} ions in the (A)-sites when their crystallite size decrease [36, 42]. In other words the cation distribution (i) is the result of the physical state of CF crystallite: size (D) and strain (ε). **We empirically derived the following equation for the spin-canting angle which is** written as a sum of size (D_ϕ) and strain (ε_ϕ) contributions (solid line in Fig.5):

$$\phi = c\phi_0[(e^{t/D} - 1) + (e^{\gamma\varepsilon} - 1)] \quad (6)$$

where ϕ_0 is the value of the spin-canting angle at $i = 0$ (from the linear fit: $\phi_0 = 72^\circ$), t is the thickness of the dead layer ($t = 1.2$ nm [36]), $D_\phi = e^{t/D} - 1$ and $\varepsilon_\phi = e^{\gamma\varepsilon} - 1$ are the size and strain contributions, respectively, and c and γ are constants. In our case, using $c = 3.1$ and $\gamma = 5.3$, ϕ is slightly shifted from zero for the as-calcined powders, due to the size contribution $D_\phi = 0.003$. For the powders milled one time only, with crystal size close to the single domain limit (28 nm [43]) the strain contribution accounts for 76 % in moving from the Néel model, and its weight drops to 31 % after the second milling step where the powders are less able to arrange microstrain and display a crystallite size close to the superparamagnetic limit (6 nm [35]), $D_\phi = 0.14$.

Fig. 5 The variation of ϕ angle with i plot as experimental points and their linear fit (dashed line); and the variation of ϕ angle in function of the measured crystallite sizes and strains (solid line) according with the reported equation ($c = 3.1$, $t = 1.2$ nm, and $\gamma = 5.3$). (single column)

K_j values (Tab. 3 and Tab. 4) are in agreement with the trend measured for the coercivity, and are comparable with those reported in literature for milled CF nanopowder: 12.9 Merg/cm^3 at 5 K , and 5.2 Merg/cm^3 at 300 K [21]. Although M_S can be directly obtained from the M vs. H curves at any temperature, the determination of K_1 at room temperature is more complex since parts of the samples are blocked and parts are unblocked. The differentiated initial magnetization curves (Fig.6) represent the irreversible component of the susceptibility ($\chi_{\text{irr}}=dM/dH$). In other words, this quantity can be considered as a measure of the energy barrier distribution correlated to the distribution of particle coercive fields. The values of irreversible susceptibility peak ($\chi_{\text{irr-p}}$) (reported in Tab. 3 and Tab. 4, for CF₁₁ and CF₁₃ sample, respectively) are in agreement with the coercivity trends observed in the M vs. H curves. It is worth underlining that at 5 K - when all samples behave as blocked ferrimagnets - the high symmetry of the single peak in χ_{irr} clearly indicates the presence of a unique magnetic phase [44], confirming the morpho-structural characterization (i.e. XRD and Mössbauer analysis) and M vs. H measurements, while at higher temperature the symmetry loss indicates that parts of the samples are blocked and parts are unblocked, as expected due to the observed particle size distribution especially for the sample milled one time (Fig.1 (g) and (h)). In addition it should be underlined that both CF₁₁M_I and CF₁₃M_I nanoparticles exhibit a $\chi_{\text{irr-p}}$ centred at a higher magnetic field with respect to that reported in the literature (15.5 kOe) [31].

Fig. 6 Irreversible susceptibility ($\chi_{\text{irr}} = dM/dH$) of the samples CF₁₁ (first column) and CF₁₃ (second column).
(two- column)

The reduced remnant magnetization (M_r/M_s) values at 5 K for as synthesised samples (CF₁₁ and CF₁₃) are in full agreement with the theoretical value for the pure cubic anisotropy. The decrease of that value with the milling treatments suggests that CF particles have a mixed cubic/uniaxial anisotropy [31]. In fact, M_r/M_s is correlated to the nature of the anisotropy symmetry, since the expected value for randomly oriented and completely blocked nanoparticles are $M_r/M_s = 0.5$ and $M_r/M_s = 0.83$ for uniaxial and cubic anisotropy, respectively. In the case of milled CF particles, these two components are mainly associated to the magneto-crystalline (cubic, K_I) and stress (uniaxial, K_s) terms, and the effective magnetic anisotropy can be expressed as $K_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{(K_I^2 + K_s^2)}$ [21] even if the effective magnetic anisotropy K_{eff} contains different contributions such as shape, and surface (usually it is the dominant term when the particle size is under 5 nm [44]). The stress anisotropy is related to the residual strain as $K_s = 3/2\lambda\varepsilon E$, where $\lambda = 110$ ppm and $E = 142$ GPa are the average magnetostriction constant and the Young's modulus, respectively [21]. The milled CF₁₁M_I and CF₁₃M_I display a K_{eff} of 46 Merg/cm³ and 50 Merg/cm³, respectively, which are higher than 45 Merg/cm³ reported by Liu *et al.* for CF powders with high level of strain and high density of defects introduced by time optimization of the milling treatment [21]. This optimization allows to increase the maximum energy product, $(BH)_{\text{max}}$, up to 2.16 MGOe and 17.54 MGOe at 300 K and 5 K, respectively (all the $(BH)_{\text{max}}$ values are reported in Tab. 3 and Tab. 4). $(BH)_{\text{max}}$ is the area of the largest rectangle that can be inscribed under the curve of magnetic induction (B) as a function of the applied field (H), and represents the figure of merit of a permanent magnet [45]. Ponce *et al.* have increased $(BH)_{\text{max}}$ of CF particles from 0.5 MGOe to 1.1 MGOe by increasing the strain from 0.3 % to 1.0 % through milling treatments, and have considered $(BH)_{\text{max}}$ to be correlated to H_c and M_r (respectively, 1.9 kOe and 29.2 emu/g for un-milled powders, and 4.1 kOe and 36.8 emu/g for the milled ones) [33]. The results presented by Ponce *et al.* are in agreement with our evidences. On the other side, in a recent work, López-Ortega *et al.* made a significant breakthrough; they have increased $(BH)_{\text{max}}$ up to 2.1 MGOe and 5.4 MGOe at 300 K and 5 K, respectively, by enhancing K_{eff} , through the size-dependent surface anisotropy and the morphology-controlled shape anisotropy, while keeping negligible the overall level of strain, and smaller H_c (about 3 kOe) [6]. This result was achieved by enhancing the magnetic

moment ($M_s \approx 80$ emu/g) through an iron excess in the stoichiometry (Fe/Co = 4 instead of 2), and controlling the particle shape and size close to, but bigger than, the coherent radius. Our results confirm the strong relationship existing between K_{eff} and $(BH)_{max}$, as claimed by López-Ortega *et al.*, but we disagree with the statement that “only large M_s [...] can efficiently increase the $(BH)_{max}$ product” [6]. In fact, even if smaller M_s were obtained, we found larger $(BH)_{max}$ products at 5 K and 300 K. In our opinion, this result can be ascribed to the high defect’s density and high strain level induced by the milling treatments. It deserves to be noted the perfect linear correlation ($R^2 = 1$) between the $(BH)_{max}$ values at 5 K and the calculated ϵ (Tab. 1) or K_{eff} (Tab. 3 and Tab. 4) for both series of samples: CF₁₁-CF₁₁M_I-CF₁₁M_{II}, and CF₁₃-CF₁₃M_I-CF₁₃M_{II}. Moreover the much higher $(BH)_{max}$ product that we have obtained at 5 K respect to those presented by López-Ortega *et al.* can be mainly ascribed to the enhancement of K_{eff} as a consequence of the high K_s achieved with the milling. Thus the tailoring of the crystallite size and microstrain of CF (here synthesized by solid state reaction, but not exclusively) through mechanical milling can be considered as a suitable strategy to produce CF as permanent magnet. The greater efficiency of the milling in introducing high level of strain and density defects into large-size CF grains synthesized by SSR respect to those synthesized by precipitation methods is also confirmed by the higher H_c and H_c/K_I increase rates of 431% and 12.2% if compared to those reported by Liu *et al.* of 360% and 9%, respectively [21]. After the second milling step K_{eff} decreases to 15 Merg/cm³ and 28 Merg/cm³ for CF₁₁M_{II} and CF₁₃M_{II} samples, respectively, as a result of further reduction of the crystallites size and the consequent less ability to arrange microstrain. The increase of coercivity due to the pinning effect of the introduced residual strain and defects, and their presence also after the second milling treatment are confirmed, according with the Wohlfarth’s relation: $\chi_i = 1/3M_s^2/K_I$ [46], by the decrease of initial susceptibility χ_i of about 50% between the as calcined and the milled powders. As further evidence, it was found that $H_c(T)/M_s(T)$ ratio is linearly correlated to $K_I^{3/2}(T)/M_s^2(T)$, and $K_I^{1/2}(T)/M_s^2(T)$ for the as calcined and milled CF powders, respectively. This means, according with the micromagnetic model [23], that for as calcined CF powders the domain wall is pinned by extended planar inhomogeneities (average half width of the magnetic inhomogeneities, r_0 , larger than domain wall width, δ_B) such as dislocations and twin boundaries on {111} planes as expected for annealed micrometer particles [22]. After milling the coercivity is controlled by magnetic inhomogeneities with the size smaller than the domain wall width (thin planar inhomogeneities, $r_0 < \delta_B$).

From the temperature dependence of the coercive field (Fig.7) it can be seen that the first milling treatment increases the uniaxial anisotropy as the H_c vs. T experimental points are very well fitted by $H_c = a - bT^{3/4}$ (Fig.7) which describes the behaviour of many randomly oriented single-domain magnetic particles presenting uniaxial anisotropy [47]. The second milling treatment further reduces the exponential coefficient and the temperature dependence of coercivity could be expressed in terms of $T^{1/2}$, i.e., $H_c = a - bT^{1/2}$ (Fig.7), indicating that CF nanoparticles may form a system with the easy directions of the particles oriented parallel to the magnetic field [47], as expected, since for smaller particles, coherent rotation is predominant whereas for larger particles the development of domain walls is favourable [40]. As the relaxation time of a magnetic particle decreases with increasing temperature, we can define a characteristic temperature, called the deblocking temperature (T_{db}), above which the magnetic moment of the particles appears unblocked with respect to the time scale of the experiment, and the magnetization in the presence of a magnetic field reaches its thermal equilibrium value. In this state ($T \geq T_{db}$), called superparamagnetic, the magnetic moment of a single superparamagnetic particle is much higher than that of an atomic paramagnet, and the remanence and coercivity of the system vanish [48]. Thus, the deblocking temperature T_{db} is assumed to be equal to the thermal value corresponding to $H_c = 0$. The obtained T_{db} values show that the first milling treatment remarkably increases the deblocking temperature, as well as the coercivity (insets in Fig.4), while the second one, leading the nanoparticles to the superparamagnetic size, reduces T_{db} at temperatures lower than that of the multidomain as-calcined CF particles. The shifting of T_{db} over 420 K is a good indication that the $CF_{11}M_I$ and $CF_{13}M_I$ nanoparticles are suitable for a wide variety of technological applications that require temperatures higher than room temperature, for example, medical applications where magnetocaloric properties can achieve local hyperthermia, e.g., at cancer sites. It is worth underlining that the $CF_{11}M_{II}$ can show a superparamagnetic behaviour just at two tens of degrees higher than the room temperature. **Even if the multi-step milling seems to be promising in the production of superparamagnetic CF particles, the obtained low M_s values, may limit their application in magnetic fluid hyperthermia [7, 17].**

Fig. 7 Variation of the coercive force (H_c) with temperature (T). (single column)

The temperature dependence of the zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetizations, measured with an applied field of 100 Oe, is shown in Fig.8. Since the observed irreversibility is due to the characteristic blocking-unblocking process of the particle magnetic moment, the bending of FC curves of the samples CF₁₁M_{II} and CF₁₃M_{II} confirm that the second milling decreases the deblocking temperature, while the small difference between T_{db} and T_{cross} (the interception between ZFC and FC) gives an indication of the narrowness of the anisotropy energy barrier distribution of the CF₁₁M_{II} particles [48]. Moreover, T_{cross} , in principle, differs from the blocking temperature since the system, due to the absence of capping ligands on the surfaces, is strongly interacting. The T_{cross} values of the other samples is unknown, being higher than the maximum temperature (390 K) reached in the measurement.

Fig. 8 ZFC and FC normalized magnetization, measured with a magnetic field of $H = 100$ Oe. (*single column*)

3. Conclusions

Nanosized cobalt ferrite was produced by conventional solid state reaction followed by multi-step planetary milling. This technological process allows an easy batch-scale production of cobalt ferrite nanopowders with tunable properties. High-coercivity (3.7 kOe) cobalt ferrite nanopowders (33 nm) were produced by calcination of the oxide precursors at 1320 K and one-step planetary milling with large milling media (5 mm). Nanosized cobalt ferrite (12 nm), characterized by small magnetic hysteresis loop ($H_c = 250$ Oe), was produced by calcination at 1120 K and two-step planetary milling with smaller diameter of the milling media (1 mm). The planetary milling setup was designed in order to induce high level of strain in the milled powders at each milling step. **This strategy allows to produce cobalt ferrite particles characterized by very high maximum energy product ($(BH)_{max} = 2.16$ MGOe) required for the permanent magnet applications.** The microstructural **modifications** were correlated to the magnetic properties and discussed in agreement with the literature: (i) cobalt ferrite particles with crystallite size close to the single-domain limit displays the highest coercivity which decreases at the decreasing of crystallite size toward the superparamagnetic limit; (ii) **the** milling treatments introduce small magnetic defects with a pinning effect for the magnetic domain wall motion larger than that of extended planar inhomogeneities such as twinning boundaries, which are present in the as-calcined cobalt ferrite; (iii) microstrains increase the uniaxial anisotropy, as demonstrated by the coercivity trend as a function of temperature, shift the degree of inversion, **and enhance the maximum energy product.** Finally, we suggest that the degree of inversion is the result of the crystallite size and strain level

and that the shift from the Néel model (spin-canting angle) can be calculated as a sum of crystallite size and strain contributions.

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Figures

Fig. 1 SEM morphology of as calcined (a) CF_{11} and (b) CF_{13} powders; after the first milling step (c) $CF_{11}M_I$ and (d) $CF_{13}M_I$ powders ; and after the second milling step (e) $CF_{11}M_{II}$ and (f) $CF_{13}M_{II}$ powders. The cumulative curves show the measured PS values through image analysis of the SEM micrographs. The corresponding particle size density distributions were obtained by deriving the fitting of the experimental points. The cumulative curves of the as-calcined and the two times milled powders were fitted through the SGompertz model implemented in OringPro 9.1 software, while for the powders milled one time the biphasic Dose response function was used. (two- column)

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of the CF powders as calcined and after planetary milling treatments. All the patterns were collected in the same conditions. CF peaks are labelled with the respective Miller indices. The arrow points the highest peak of the unreacted hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$). (single column)

Fig. 3 Williamson-Hall plot obtained from the Lorentzian broadening contribution measured with Rietveld refinement. (single column)

Fig. 4 Magnetisation (M) versus magnetic field strength (H) curves at 300 K (first row), 100 K (second row), and 5 K (third row) of CF_{11} (first column) and CF_{13} (second column) samples after calcination (square symbol), after first milling (circular symbol), and after second milling (triangular symbol). (two- column)

Fig. 5 The variation of ϕ angle with i plot as experimental points and their linear fit (dashed line); and the variation of ϕ angle as function of the measured crystallite sizes and strains (solid line) according with the reported empirical equation ($c = 3.1$, $t = 1.2$ nm, and $\gamma = 5.3$). (single column)

Fig. 6 Irreversible susceptibility ($\chi_{\text{irr}} = dM/dH$) of the samples CF_{11} (first column) and CF_{13} (second column). (two- column)

Fig. 7 Variation of the coercive force (H_c) with temperature (T). (single column)

Fig. 8 ZFC and FC normalized magnetization, measured with a magnetic field of $H = 100$ Oe. (single column)